

Supporting Information for

Species-specific loss of genetic diversity and exposure of deleterious mutations following agricultural intensification

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Supporting Methods

Correction of post-mortem DNA damage in historical samples. We investigated two methods to account for post-mortem DNA damage in historical samples: I) recalibration of putatively damaged bases using MapDamage2 (1), and II) removal of transitions, where most DNA damage is expected to occur (2, 3). We assessed their performance by comparing identity by state (IBS) similarity to the reference at filtered sites between the two correction methods and the uncorrected data (Figure S2). We estimated IBS similarity to the reference for each sample using ANGSD (4), sampling a single base at each position (-doIBS 1), counting reference bases as 1 and non-reference bases as 0 (-doMajorMinor 4 -output01 1). We calculated the average IBS similarity per individual from these values, with 1 indicating complete similarity to the reference and 0 indicating complete dissimilarity.

Historical samples without correction had less similarity to the reference than modern (Figure S2), as expected for historical samples without substantial mapping bias due to drift from the sampling time of the historical samples and the modern reference as well as differences introduced by post-mortem DNA damage (5, 6). After MapDamage2 rescaling, historical samples showed higher similarity to the reference than modern samples in *Po. icarus* and *Pl. argus*, suggesting that this method introduced dataset specific reference biases. As transition removal did not introduce this same reference bias, instead maintaining expectations for historical DNA samples when compared to a modern reference, we proceeded using transition removal in all analyses. For genotype likelihood based analyses, we excluded transitions using the ANGSD options -noTrans 1 for SAF based analyses and -rmTrans 1 for SNP based analyses. For genotype call based analyses, we removed transitions directly from the BCF using custom awk code.

Supporting Figures and Tables

Figure S1. Examples of DNA damage profiles for historical samples. Damage profiles produced by DamageProfiler (7) for the samples with the greatest (upper), median (middle), and least (lower) DNA damage in the focal species dataset are shown. In all analyses, we accounted for these misincorporations by removing transition variants.

Figure S2. Examining effects of ancient DNA damage correction methods. We estimated the identity by state (IBS) similarity to the reference for each sample (A) with no corrections for post-mortem DNA damage, (B) with transitions from the reference removed, and (C) with putatively damaged bases rescaled using MapDamage2. When no corrections were made, we observed all historical samples were more distant to the reference than modern, as is expected due to drift between the sampling time of the historical samples and the modern reference, as well as differences due to post-mortem DNA damage. Removal of transitions increased similarity to the reference, and decreased variance in IBS scores for historical samples, but did not cause historical samples to be biased towards the reference compared to the modern samples, suggesting it removes most of the DNA damage without inducing reference bias. MapDamage rescaling introduces reference bias in a way that appears sample and species specific, as variance in IBS scores increases and historical samples become more similar to the reference in historical samples compared to modern in *P. icarus* and *P. argus*. Based on this comparison, we moved forward with transition removal as the primary means to account for post-mortem DNA damage in the analyses.

Figure S3. Effect sizes for modern-historical population comparisons of (A) nucleotide diversity, (B) Watterson's θ , and (C) Tajima's D . For each of these metrics, we compared population-level windowed estimates between corresponding historical and modern populations using a Wilcoxon ranked-sign test, pairing the windows with data in both populations. To account for variation in sample count, we subsampled each population 100 times to 4 individuals and performed the test on each of the 100 subsamples. We performed this both for all samples at full sequencing depth and subsampled to 3X sequencing depth to account for variation in sequencing depth. This provided a range of effect sizes for the 100 tests, measured as the Z-score divided by the square root of the number of windows used in the test. We considered the estimated metric from modern populations to be significantly different from the corresponding historical population metric if the effect sizes of all 100 subsamplings did not overlap 0. A negative effect size represents a decrease in the metric and a positive represents an increase.

Po. icarus

Pl. argus

Cy. semiargus

Figure S4. Correlation of residuals for the focal species' admixture analyses. For each value of K in the three focal species, we assessed the goodness of fit of our data to that K model of admixture using evalAdmix (8), visualized here with the pairwise correlation of residuals between individuals (upper left triangle of the matrix). When individuals are more similar than the model suggests, they have a positive pairwise correlation, when they are more different, they have a negative. Well-fitting sample pairs have a score of 0. The lower right triangle of the matrix shows the average scores of individuals in our *a priori* population groupings, illustrating when it is largely a population's fit that is in need of improvement. While we select $K = 2$ as our best fit based on our convergence criteria for *Po. icarus* and *Pl. argus*, we see that the data does not necessarily fit the model well in *Pl. argus*, illustrating that there is greater population structure within the historical and modern time periods than $K=2$ captures, as supported by the PCA in Figure 2. Our inability to achieve convergence for K -values above 2 in these species may relate to additional clusters being explained by a relatively small proportion of the genetic variance, requiring higher sample sizes to accurately assign admixture proportions at higher K s. We do select a higher K , $K = 5$, for *Cy. semiargus*, which shows relatively good fit.

P. icarus

P. argus

C. semiargus

Figure S5. Admixture analysis results for K 2-10 for the three focal species. For each species, an admixture analysis was run for 2-10 clusters (K), with the optimized results for each value of K displayed in the figure above. We selected the best fitting K as the highest value of K that converged within 100 replicate runs of NGSadmix, following Pečnerová et al (9). The best fit values of K for each species are depicted in Figure 2 of the main text and are 2, 2, and 5 for *Po. icarus*, *Pl. argus*, and *Cy. semiargus*, respectively.

Figure S6. Relationship between the cumulative length of runs of homozygosity (RoHs) and their total count. Inbreeding coefficients can depend on both background relatedness in small populations and close-kin matings (10). Generally, a linear relationship is expected between the cumulative length of RoHs and their total count in an individual, with individuals that have an exceptionally long cumulative length of RoHs for their RoH count stemming from closer kin inbreeding events compared to others. Here, we illustrate this relationship for modern *Cy. semiargus* individuals (small points), along with their population averages (large point). We find that while there generally appears to be a similar relationship across populations, individuals with longer cumulative RoH length (and thus higher inbreeding coefficients) tend to slightly deviate from the general trend, having fewer RoH than would be expected given their cumulative length. This suggests that these have recent close-kin inbreeding backgrounds and are more common in the Småland and SE Skåne populations.

Figure S7. Linear models examining the relationship between individual inbreeding coefficient and deleterious burden in modern *Cy. semiargus* across three variant subsets. Red points and lines depict total estimates of deleterious burden, measured as counts of alternate (high and moderate impact) or derived (conserved regions) alleles for the given putatively deleterious category per alternate/derived allele. Blue points and lines depict homozygous deleterious burden, measured in the same way, but only counting homozygous alternate/derived genotypes in the numerator. Total deleterious burden has no significant relationship with inbreeding coefficients for any variant category, whereas homozygous deleterious burden is positively related to inbreeding coefficient across all variant categories.

Figure S8. Retention of heterozygosity over time per species, subsampled to equivalent sequencing depth. Changes in heterozygosity predicted over 100 years based on the rate of change estimated from modern and historical samples for each of 11 species (A), including subsampling to equivalent sequencing depths of (B) 3X, and (C) 2X, across samples. Species with a value of 0 have all samples in one category (modern or historical) with a sequencing depth lower than the target, so cannot be compared at the target depth. Species are grouped by conservation status, which follows the species name on the x-axis. Background coloration refers to the three genetic decline thresholds outlined by Andersson et al (11), where a retention of $\geq 95\%$ over 100 year is considered 'acceptable' (green), a retention of 75-94% as 'warning' (yellow), and a retention of $< 75\%$ as 'alarm' (red). Points represent mean estimates for change in heterozygosity across all sample pairs for a species. Species with error bars have more than one possible sample pair, with error bars illustrating the spread of estimates across all modern/historical sample pairs. Species with a * next to their species name on the x-axis have been mapped to a related species' reference genome as they lack a species-specific genome.

(A) Multi-sample BCF with MAF > 0, without --ignore-homref

(B) Multi-sample BCF with MAF > 0, with --ignore-homref (method in manuscript)

Figure S9. Impacts of including homozygous reference genotypes when estimating runs of homozygosity. BCFtools/RoH utilizes deviations from Hardy-Weinberg to detect runs of homozygosity, requiring an allele frequency for each variant to estimate this. In datasets where allele frequencies are unknown, a default can be used, commonly a minor allele frequency of 0.4. However, singleton and other low frequency variants deviate considerably from this default, and can heavily inflate the estimated runs of homozygosity, as in (A) where nearly all individuals of *Po. icarus* in our dataset are described as having almost the entire genome in runs of homozygosity. Two potential mechanisms to address this would be to estimate allele frequencies for the populations and supply them (as we previously did for the modern samples of *Po. icarus* in (12)), or filter out low frequency variants with a minor allele frequency filter. We have considerable variation in sample sizes across our species datasets, making a consistent MAF filter or comparable allele frequency estimates challenging, so we did not use either of these approaches. Instead, we utilized the option to ignore homozygous reference variants, with the results shown in (B). This reduces the effect, as the inflation largely comes from homozygous reference variants present in the BCF due to rare, alternate variants present in other individuals. When performed in this way, the analysis is similar to that done for variants called from a single sample the single sample as described in BCFtools online guide (<https://samtools.github.io/bcftools/howtos/roh-calling.html>). Using this approach, the estimates we get for all individuals show less than 1.5% of the genome in runs of homozygosity for all individuals, in line with the estimates we generated using population specific allele frequencies in (12). One main difference to performing the analysis on a single sample is that by using a multi-sample BCF, we filter out alternate variants that are fixed in the study individuals, as the reference allele is unlikely segregating, or segregating in low frequency, in the study populations, and would deviate from our default allele frequency.

Table S1. Sample collection and sequencing information. Each sample utilized in this study is listed here, providing its sample ID as referenced in the manuscript text/figures/code. Each specimen was registered into the entomological collections of the Biological Museum at Lund University, if it was not already, and has its museum identifier provided (MZLU ID). Each specimen is assigned a Time Period, which corresponds to whether it is being treated in the Historical or Modern sample grouping. As some samples in the Modern category were pinned specimens, the origin of the tissue used for DNA extraction is provided (Tissue Source). Study Region refers to the population grouping for population level analyses, grouping samples in the same study region and time period together. Sampling Locality refers to the name of the locality in which the sample was collected, either using the authors' designation for a sampling locality for fresh specimens or using the locality listed on the label for pinned specimens. For both, latitude and longitude of the locality is provided. For fresh specimens, these values correspond to the specific location at which butterflies were sampled, for pinned specimens these coordinates are inferred from the locality listed on the label, which is usually the nearest parish from the actual sampled grassland patch. For both fresh and pinned samples, the collection date and collector are provided, with collection dates that could not be fully inferred from the label having missing information replaced with 'x'. For each sample, we report the total percent of sequencing reads mapping to the reference genome (% Mapped Reads), the mean and standard deviation of sequencing depth with no filtering (Unfiltered Depth), the mean and standard deviation sequencing depth at filtered sites and with mapping and base quality filters (Filtered Depth), as well as the IBS similarity to the reference after transition removal and filtering (where 0 is complete dissimilarity to the reference and 1 is identical to the reference).

Sample ID	MZLU ID	Species	Time Period	Tissue Source	Sex	Collect Date	Study Region	Sampling Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Collector	% Mapped Reads	Unfiltered Depth (Mean)	Unfiltered Depth (St.Dev)	Filtered Depth (Mean)	Filtered Depth (St.Dev)	Filtered Depth IBS to Ref. (No transitions, filtered sites)
MZLULEP1724	MZLULEP1724	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-03	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	90.25	6.6265	5.4377	5.3545	3.1350	0.9866
MZLULEP1868	MZLULEP1868	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-03	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	89.81	2.6829	2.7351	2.0636	1.7058	0.9870
MZLULEP1730	MZLULEP1730	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-06	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	90.26	4.3768	4.1468	3.2788	2.3432	0.9865
MZLULEP1748	MZLULEP1748	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-06	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	89.23	4.1457	3.8575	3.2049	2.2806	0.9867
MZLULEP1661	MZLULEP1661	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-07-25	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	87.85	7.7239	6.9294	6.0087	3.5081	0.9862
MZLULEP1903	MZLULEP1903	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-07-25	E Skåne	Kivik	55.685	14.2266	P. Benander	89.81	7.2553	6.0266	5.6551	3.2188	0.9863
MZLULEP3086	MZLULEP3086	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-28	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	89	7.9752	6.5168	6.7513	3.6476	0.9867
MZLULEP3149	MZLULEP3149	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-28	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	89.19	12.3246	8.6658	10.6268	5.1391	0.9864
MZLULEP3328	MZLULEP3328	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-28	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	87.93	10.2946	7.8435	8.5762	4.5100	0.9866
MZLULEP3026	MZLULEP3026	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	88	5.0321	4.7140	3.9486	2.5271	0.9869
MZLULEP3029	MZLULEP3029	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	86.41	17.3834	12.1560	14.8029	6.9090	0.9862
MZLULEP3133	MZLULEP3133	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	87.84	5.1226	4.4193	4.2546	2.6314	0.9870
MZLULEP3256	MZLULEP3256	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	90.44	8.2462	6.1114	6.8939	3.8102	0.9866
MZLULEP3259	MZLULEP3259	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	86.78	5.1091	4.3546	4.2641	2.7075	0.9871
MZLULEP3266	MZLULEP3266	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	88.75	8.1410	6.4498	6.8715	3.8162	0.9867
MZLULEP3313	MZLULEP3313	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-07-30	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	86.47	5.9142	5.3877	4.9108	2.9327	0.9868
MZLULEP3088	MZLULEP3088	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1940-08-01	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	Winblad, Gustaf	88.21	7.6368	8.4342	6.2758	4.8147	0.9865
MZLULEP4555	MZLULEP4555	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-08	W Skåne	Södra sandby	55.7169	13.3472	Ander, Kjell	87.5	3.7991	3.4718	3.0372	2.1427	0.9869
MZLULEP3679	MZLULEP3679	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-12	W Skåne	Billebjer	55.6883	13.3172	Ander, Kjell	90.1	10.9976	8.6709	8.6513	4.4733	0.9861
MZLULEP4538	MZLULEP4538	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-06-24	W Skåne	Kungsmarken	55.7138	13.2753	Ander, Kjell	89.13	6.3750	5.4928	4.8048	3.0566	0.9864
MZLULEP3661	MZLULEP3661	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-07-06	W Skåne	Kungsmarken	55.7138	13.2753	Ander, Kjell	88.41	4.5641	4.2894	3.5043	2.4050	0.9868
MZLULEP1710	MZLULEP1710	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-02	W Skåne	Södra sandby	55.7169	13.3472	Nordström, FGD	86.05	6.3371	7.0849	5.1326	3.8026	0.9858
MZLULEP1824	MZLULEP1824	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-02	W Skåne	Södra sandby	55.7169	13.3472	Nordström, FGD	90.33	4.9054	8.5379	3.4309	3.5763	0.9850
MZLULEP1709	MZLULEP1709	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-20	W Skåne	Södra sandby	55.7169	13.3472	Nordström, FGD	86.77	6.8962	7.1517	5.6940	3.6827	0.9865
MZLULEP1911	MZLULEP1911	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-20	W Skåne	Dalby	55.6648	13.3476	Nordström, FGD	64.56	4.8392	6.3971	6.6598	2.8141	0.9859
MZLULEP3656	MZLULEP3656	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-31	W Skåne	Hällestad	55.6667	13.4167	Ander, Kjell	79.12	15.6784	12.0267	12.8342	6.5288	0.9858
MZLULEP3668	MZLULEP3668	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-31	W Skåne	Hällestad	55.6667	13.4167	Ander, Kjell	88.73	5.1566	4.7107	3.9986	2.7636	0.9868
MZLULEP4316	MZLULEP4316	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1934-08-31	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4209	Ander, Kjell	63.95	4.0737	3.9557	3.1755	2.3562	0.9865
PI200	MZLU00126549	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.45	24.2990	19.3371	25.9004	8.9500	0.9869
PI201	MZLU00126550	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.48	24.1770	19.3767	25.6338	8.8191	0.9869
PI202	MZLU00126551	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.42	24.9305	19.7051	26.6182	9.1724	0.9869
PI203	MZLU00126552	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.48	22.2730	16.7684	23.8296	8.3121	0.9869
PI204	MZLU00126553	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.46	28.3342	22.4784	30.1675	10.1507	0.9869
PI205	MZLU00126554	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-17	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	98.8	19.8327	15.7252	21.1057	7.5297	0.9869
PI206	MZLU00126555	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-19	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	96.93	24.1846	18.8576	25.7285	8.8854	0.9869
PI207	MZLU00126556	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-19	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	99.03	25.0312	19.5524	26.4669	9.0634	0.9869
PI208	MZLU00126557	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-19	E Skåne	Haväng	55.7223	14.188	ZJ Nolen	98.83	25.2565	19.2321	26.9509	9.2542	0.9869
PI413	MZLU00126558	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.4	41.4369	30.2651	44.1938	14.3475	0.9871
PI414	MZLU00126559	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.41	45.0198	32.4127	48.0057	15.3341	0.9871
PI415	MZLU00126560	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.38	52.2610	36.7243	55.7199	17.5443	0.9871
PI417	MZLU00126561	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.39	46.5902	33.2564	49.6235	15.9563	0.9871
PI418	MZLU00126562	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.07	43.0788	31.1873	45.7850	14.8659	0.9871
PI419	MZLU00126563	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.4	41.5108	30.9450	43.7834	14.3534	0.9871
PI420	MZLU00126564	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.39	36.3402	26.9763	38.3713	12.7433	0.9870
PI421	MZLU00126565	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.41	42.7424	31.0190	45.4363	14.6485	0.9871
PI422	MZLU00126566	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-01	Öland	Sandby Borg	56.5532	16.6396	ZJ Nolen	99.4	49.5389	34.7515	52.7779	16.7797	0.9872
PI028	MZLU00126531	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	98.65	20.1345	15.8614	21.4533	7.6299	0.9869
PI029	MZLU00126532	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.45	15.5866	12.6604	16.6068	6.2564	0.9869
PI030	MZLU00126533	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.44	26.2356	20.6572	27.8476	9.4813	0.9869
PI031	MZLU00126534	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.36	23.4252	18.1688	25.0212	8.7807	0.9869
PI032	MZLU00126535	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.46	27.6173	21.7929	29.3233	8.8977	0.9869
PI033	MZLU00126536	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.46	22.0767	17.4678	23.5427	8.3630	0.9869
PI034	MZLU00126537	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.43	22.7005	17.8005	24.1864	8.4073	0.9869

PI035	MZLU00126538	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.27	25.0408	19.6283	26.6463	9.1329	0.9869
PI036	MZLU00126539	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-07-22	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6951	13.4316	ZJ Nolen	99.44	20.4675	16.5136	21.7748	7.7244	0.9869
MZLU153003	MZLU153003	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1917-06-18	E Skåne	Åhus	55.9231	14.2942	Wahlgrén, Einar	86.18	7.4173	6.6052	5.9107	3.9996	0.9866
MZLU153166	MZLU153166	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-26	Öland	Gärdslösa	56.7842	16.7392	H. Rambring	88.25	7.9840	6.8399	6.7320	3.8774	0.9867
MZLU153167	MZLU153167	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-26	Öland	Gärdslösa	56.7842	16.7392	H. Rambring	89.11	6.3358	5.4524	5.1220	3.3508	0.9869
MZLU153168	MZLU153168	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-26	Öland	Gärdslösa	56.7842	16.7392	H. Rambring	87.21	6.4916	5.0967	5.5782	3.2545	0.9870
MZLU153169	MZLU153169	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-26	Öland	Gärdslösa	56.7842	16.7392	H. Rambring	88.84	8.6679	6.6301	7.1147	4.1660	0.9866
MZLU153170	MZLU153170	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-26	Öland	Gärdslösa	56.7842	16.7392	H. Rambring	87.86	9.0520	6.8694	7.6759	4.1854	0.9865
MZLU153046	MZLU153046	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-06-27	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	88.52	7.4877	6.8060	5.7626	3.6970	0.9863
MZLU153040	MZLU153040	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-01	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	88.43	5.3583	4.8620	4.3129	2.8472	0.9873
MZLU153045	MZLU153045	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-06	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	81.7	4.7669	4.9153	3.3885	2.6979	0.9875
MZLU153042	MZLU153042	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-07	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	88.85	6.2328	5.5258	4.9583	3.1595	0.9870
MZLU153048	MZLU153048	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-12	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	88.98	8.5399	7.6795	6.4449	3.9946	0.9866
MZLU152940	MZLU152940	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1943-07-03	W Skåne	Hällestad	55.6765	13.4192	Ander, Kjell	89.71	6.6791	5.2941	5.4009	3.3093	0.9871
PLAR0200	MZLU00126622	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.24	15.4421	11.3764	16.3566	5.8562	0.9876
PLAR0202	MZLU00126623	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.23	10.8777	8.3850	11.5157	4.5444	0.9875
PLAR0203	MZLU00126624	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.23	9.5697	7.7539	10.1699	4.1624	0.9876
PLAR0208	MZLU00126625	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.2	8.4690	6.9970	8.8649	3.7840	0.9875
PLAR0211	MZLU00126626	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.21	9.5544	7.4132	10.1360	4.1544	0.9875
PLAR0217	MZLU00126627	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.22	11.2184	8.6247	11.8648	4.6227	0.9875
PLAR0222	MZLU00126628	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.21	10.0108	7.6582	10.6211	4.2795	0.9875
PLAR0216	MZLU00126629	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-07-06	E Skåne	Drakamöllan	55.7551	14.1252	Melina Eberhagen	99.23	10.4967	8.2212	11.1103	4.4360	0.9875
MZLU107434	MZLU107434	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.26	17.6742	13.2350	18.5586	6.6817	0.9878
MZLU107438	MZLU107438	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.24	23.2913	16.8643	24.3292	8.3377	0.9878
MZLU107435	MZLU107435	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.24	26.4675	18.7992	27.5389	9.1195	0.9878
MZLU107436	MZLU107436	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.26	15.7820	11.6788	16.6375	6.1641	0.9879
MZLU107470	MZLU107470	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.26	19.5632	13.4582	20.6388	7.2203	0.9878
MZLU107486	MZLU107486	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.25	10.1244	7.7158	10.6598	4.6094	0.9879
MZLU107469	MZLU107469	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	99.26	17.6840	13.0833	18.7171	6.7356	0.9878
MZLU107483	MZLU107483	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen	98.95	6.5638	6.3889	6.8987	3.2892	0.9879
MZLU107445	MZLU107445	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.08	28.6293	19.5327	30.0373	9.8946	0.9878
MZLU107449	MZLU107449	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.28	19.3055	13.9622	20.3189	7.1835	0.9878
MZLU107451	MZLU107451	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.19	18.7120	13.7977	19.6705	6.8977	0.9879
MZLU107471	MZLU107471	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.27	23.5678	16.1260	24.9477	8.4534	0.9878
MZLU107477	MZLU107477	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.15	12.0313	9.3738	12.7486	5.0391	0.9879
MZLU107487	MZLU107487	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Jordtorpåsén	56.6783	16.5511	ZJ Nolen	99.25	11.3331	9.6432	11.9793	4.8525	0.9878
MZLU107426	MZLU107426	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.26	18.2802	13.3849	18.9444	6.7868	0.9878
MZLU107439	MZLU107439	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.21	18.4931	13.5925	19.3880	6.9964	0.9878
MZLU107441	MZLU107441	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.25	15.4133	11.2278	15.9880	6.0253	0.9878
MZLU107443	MZLU107443	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.26	28.9807	19.1214	30.3413	9.8250	0.9878
MZLU107468	MZLU107468	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.25	14.3171	10.5181	14.9962	5.6642	0.9879
MZLU107475	MZLU107475	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.09	30.7553	20.0868	32.3338	10.3973	0.9879
MZLU107480	MZLU107480	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-12	SW Skåne	Falsterbo	55.4025	12.8853	ZJ Nolen	99.24	9.8014	7.5806	10.2644	4.3282	0.9879
MZLU153246	MZLU153246	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1956-07-21	E Skåne	Degeberga	55.838	14.0901	H. Rambring	87.79	8.5362	5.8164	7.4049	3.8144	0.9943
MZLU153247	MZLU153247	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1956-07-21	E Skåne	Degeberga	55.838	14.0901	H. Rambring	91.55	9.2474	6.2327	8.2820	4.0466	0.9942
MZLU153248	MZLU153248	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1956-07-21	E Skåne	Degeberga	55.838	14.0901	H. Rambring	88.75	8.1874	5.8511	6.9891	3.6274	0.9942
MZLU153251	MZLU153251	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1956-07-21	E Skåne	Degeberga	55.838	14.0901	H. Rambring	87.62	9.3111	6.1496	8.1991	3.9924	0.9943
MZLU153250	MZLU153250	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1957-07-21	E Skåne	Degeberga	55.838	14.0901	H. Rambring	92.47	10.8848	7.8682	8.9742	4.7141	0.9939
MZLU152770	MZLU152770	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-06-27	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	90.47	8.6375	7.8534	5.9420	3.4702	0.9941
MZLU152769	MZLU152769	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-06-29	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	90.34	13.2426	9.2493	11.0995	5.0145	0.9941
MZLU152765	MZLU152765	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-01	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	92.27	7.8906	11.0634	3.2553	2.5113	0.9944
MZLU152766	MZLU152766	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1936-07-07	Småland	Hjelmseryd	57.3112	14.5131	Carlgrén G.	92.17	7.7414	8.4704	4.9316	3.6116	0.9944
MZLU153204	MZLU153204	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-06-19	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4214	H. Rambring	92.39	9.0471	6.6950	7.5780	4.0799	0.9942
MZLU153205	MZLU153205	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-06-19	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4214	H. Rambring	89.85	8.5326	6.3555	7.3761	3.8271	0.9942
MZLU153206	MZLU153206	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-06-19	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4214	H. Rambring	92.53	8.2745	6.1955	6.7965	3.6301	0.9944
MZLU153216	MZLU153216	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-06-19	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4214	H. Rambring	87.08	7.2059	5.5914	5.7934	3.2882	0.9944
MZLU153221	MZLU153221	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-06-19	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4214	H. Rambring	93.52	6.1028	4.8362	5.1551	3.1059	0.9945

MZLU107504	MZLU107504	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-03	E Skåne	Fåstan	55.776	14.1722	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.66	13.8575	8.4983	14.3069	4.8855	0.9947
MZLU107506	MZLU107506	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-03	E Skåne	Fåstan	55.776	14.1722	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.53	12.8013	7.9115	13.2222	4.6477	0.9947
MZLU107507	MZLU107507	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-03	E Skåne	Fåstan	55.776	14.1722	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.62	13.9124	8.5575	14.3866	4.8926	0.9948
CYSE0078	MZLU00107520	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-06-23	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.64	14.5870	8.8719	15.2217	5.0534	0.9943
CYSE0094	MZLU00107522	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-06-27	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	97.84	12.2923	7.9741	12.8138	4.5144	0.9942
CYSE0096	MZLU00107523	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-06-27	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.22	6.9388	5.3837	7.2874	3.1503	0.9943
CYSE0098	MZLU00107524	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-06-27	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.64	12.1931	7.7005	12.7443	4.4728	0.9942
CYSE0116	MZLU00107525	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2022-06-28	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.62	10.3753	7.3304	10.8166	4.0007	0.9943
CYSE0198	MZLU00107526	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	F	2022-07-01	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.48	12.7517	8.9254	13.4248	4.6371	0.9942
CYSE0199	MZLU00107527	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	F	2022-07-01	SE Skåne	SE Skåne	55.3864	14.1014	Melina Eberhagen	99.44	10.1950	7.3583	10.7346	4.0043	0.9942
MZLU107461	MZLU107461	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	F	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.5	14.9776	10.0984	15.5068	5.2176	0.9945
MZLU107462	MZLU107462	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	F	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.55	19.5387	12.7790	20.3246	6.2319	0.9947
MZLU107465	MZLU107465	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-06-24	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.67	24.0444	12.8762	24.8293	7.2916	0.9947
MZLU107455	MZLU107455	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.66	12.8512	8.1119	13.2037	4.6222	0.9947
MZLU107456	MZLU107456	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.64	10.7964	7.2104	11.0813	4.1169	0.9947
MZLU107501	MZLU107501	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	F	2021-07-07	Småland	Götafors	57.492	14.1134	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.52	10.4693	8.0568	10.8983	4.1948	0.9946
MZLU107457	MZLU107457	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.66	18.4531	10.6351	19.0170	5.9458	0.9947
MZLU107460	MZLU107460	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.64	15.0318	9.2027	15.3992	5.1257	0.9947
MZLU107464	MZLU107464	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.55	14.7325	9.3554	15.1875	5.0667	0.9947
MZLU107497	MZLU107497	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	94.21	11.1978	7.7088	11.5420	4.2353	0.9947
MZLU107498	MZLU107498	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.37	11.7313	8.0881	12.0643	4.3650	0.9947
MZLU107499	MZLU107499	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.66	12.4615	8.1868	12.8291	4.5145	0.9947
MZLU107500	MZLU107500	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.56	9.2647	6.5240	9.5369	3.8667	0.9947
MZLU107505	MZLU107505	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-04	W Skåne	Silvåkra	55.6695	13.4924	ZJ Nolen; P Jametska	99.13	12.1968	8.5088	12.5605	4.5002	0.9946
MZLU166853	MZLU166853	<i>Agriades optilete</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1961-06-29	Småland	Agunnaryd	56.7318	14.2439	Nils Burrau	51.76	5.6996	21.5002	5.1681	4.0472	0.9799
MZLU107492	MZLU107492	<i>Agriades optilete</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-05	Småland	Agunnaryd	56.7318	14.2439	ZJ Nolen	92.37	6.1805	22.9025	9.2235	5.9244	0.9809
MZLU166851	MZLU166851	<i>Aricia agestis</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1939-xx-xx	W Skåne	Vomb	55.6731	13.5503	Nils Burrau	90.13	6.1470	5.2097	5.5538	2.7879	0.9928
MZLU107489	MZLU107489	<i>Aricia agestis</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2020-08-03	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6959	13.431	ZJ Nolen	99.49	6.9297	6.6422	7.5488	3.2230	0.9929
MZLU166854	MZLU166854	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1951-07-29	Öland	Vickleby	56.5766	16.4604	H. Rambring	80.11	2.1346	2.9651	1.9964	1.1719	0.9942
MZLU107493	MZLU107493	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-17	Öland	Penåsa	56.4407	16.4726	ZJ Nolen	98.77	5.6343	5.9721	6.1255	2.7048	0.9939
MZLU174144	MZLU174144	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1932-07-09	W Skåne	Arild	56.2597	12.6081	Nils Burrau	68.29	4.7024	10.8809	4.2645	3.6644	0.9812
MZLU174145	MZLU174145	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1932-07-09	W Skåne	Arild	56.2597	12.6081	Nils Burrau	67.9	5.8758	13.1512	5.5697	4.4501	0.9807
MZLU174143	MZLU174143	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Modern	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	2003-07-07	W Skåne	Börringe	55.5056	13.3592	Håkan Elmqvist	73.16	7.2672	16.0411	6.0228	4.8254	0.9804
EK001	MZLU161410	<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1967-07-18	W Skåne	Dalhem	56.0675	12.7367	Harry Rydén	40.37	4.5769	14.9906	6.3870	5.2767	0.9775
EK006	private collection	<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	Modern	Pinned Specimen (legs)	M	2003-07-18	W Skåne	Dalhem	56.0675	12.7367	Göran Engqvist	33.88	5.1858	18.3444	7.5109	8.0144	0.9786
MZLU166850	MZLU166850	<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1932-07-03	W Skåne	Torna Hällestad	55.6781	13.4209	Nils Burrau	71.14	4.5694	14.4362	3.2808	2.4453	0.9833
MZLU107491	MZLU107491	<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	Modern	Field Caught	M	2021-07-03	W Skåne	Tvedöra	55.6959	13.431	ZJ Nolen	96.57	2.6905	10.5521	3.7240	2.3272	0.9839
MZLU174141	MZLU174141	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1943-05-30	Södermanland	Murkö	58.9833	17.6667	Winblad, Gustaf	39.4	0.9854	5.0298	2.3205	2.8331	0.9800
MZLU174142	MZLU174142	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Historical	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	1944-xx-08	Södermanland	Stockholm	59.3294	18.0686	E. Norstrand	30.31	1.6735	8.6359	3.7045	3.1705	0.9775
MZLU174140	MZLU174140	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Modern	Pinned Specimen (abdomen)	M	2016-xx-xx	Södermanland	Långeaedebergen	59.2154	17.1414	Håkan Elmqvist	16.72	0.9795	6.2986	2.8717	3.4785	0.9800

Table S2. Individual estimates of heterozygosity and inbreeding (Froh). Individual heterozygosity was estimated using ANGSD. We estimated confidence intervals for each estimate of heterozygosity using 300 bootstraps of the individual SFS (resampling sites with replacement), recalculating heterozygosity for each and estimating the confidence interval from the lower 2.5% and upper 97.5% quantiles of the distribution of bootstrapped estimates. We performed this analysis for all samples at their full sequencing depth, subsampled to 3X sequencing depth, and subsampled to 2X sequencing depth to enable equivalent depth comparisons across samples. When a sample had lower than the target depth (either 3X or 2X, allowing samples with >2.9X or >1.9X depth to be included, respectively) before depth subsampling, it's heterozygosity is listed as NA in the table below. Froh estimated as the proportion of the autosomal genome in runs of homozygosity longer than 100kb. This analysis was performed using BCFtools RoH on called genotypes, subsampling all samples to 5X depth before genotype calling and excluding samples with <4.9X sequencing depth (listed as NA in the Froh column). For both analyses, transition sites were removed - skipping sites with transitions when generating the SFS for heterozygosity estimates or by completely removing transition variants from the species BCFs. For heterozygosity this means that the values are lower than true heterozygosity in the samples, instead representing only transversion heterozygous sites per 1000bp. To obtain full heterozygosity, these estimates can be multiplied by (1+(transition/transversion ratio for the species)). Froh values should not be affected by transition removal in this same way, as it is based on ranges across multiple variants, not variant counts.

Sample ID	Species	Time Period	Study Region	Heterozygous sites / 1000bp (excluding transitions; full depth)		Heterozygous sites / 1000bp (excluding transitions; 3X depth)		Heterozygous sites / 1000bp (excluding transitions; 2X depth)		Froh > 100kb
				95% CI; full depth	95% CI; 3X depth	95% CI; 2X depth				
MZLULEP1724	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.326	6.314-6.343	6.182	6.165-6.198	6.059	6.042-6.079	0.0002
MZLULEP1868	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.205	6.188-6.224	NA	NA	6.192	6.175-6.213	NA
MZLULEP1730	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.761	6.746-6.777	6.744	6.728-6.762	6.667	6.645-6.688	NA
MZLULEP1748	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.091	6.074-6.107	6.064	6.051-6.082	5.890	5.87-5.909	NA
MZLULEP1661	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.416	6.404-6.431	6.298	6.285-6.316	6.158	6.14-6.175	0.0005
MZLULEP1903	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	6.298	6.287-6.314	6.125	6.11-6.142	5.992	5.973-6.014	0.0000
MZLULEP3086	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.126	6.115-6.141	5.953	5.939-5.967	5.810	5.794-5.832	0.0000
MZLULEP3149	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.104	6.091-6.115	5.840	5.824-5.854	5.691	5.674-5.71	0.0022
MZLULEP3328	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.065	6.052-6.077	5.851	5.835-5.867	5.706	5.686-5.725	0.0035
MZLULEP3026	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.093	6.079-6.106	5.989	5.974-6.005	5.850	5.835-5.868	NA
MZLULEP3029	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.172	6.157-6.184	5.863	5.85-5.877	5.711	5.693-5.731	0.0006
MZLULEP3133	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.948	5.935-5.964	5.827	5.811-5.842	5.688	5.669-5.705	NA
MZLULEP3256	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.208	6.197-6.221	6.016	6.001-6.033	5.861	5.843-5.88	0.0000
MZLULEP3259	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.978	5.965-5.993	5.875	5.861-5.888	5.761	5.743-5.782	NA
MZLULEP3266	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.215	6.205-6.229	6.085	6.069-6.1	5.987	5.971-6.006	0.0000
MZLULEP3313	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.308	6.296-6.323	6.251	6.236-6.266	6.150	6.136-6.173	0.0015
MZLULEP3088	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.294	6.282-6.309	6.255	6.237-6.272	6.258	6.241-6.279	0.0032
MZLULEP4555	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.239	6.226-6.256	6.234	6.218-6.251	6.118	6.101-6.14	NA
MZLULEP3679	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.294	6.282-6.308	6.140	6.124-6.156	5.994	5.975-6.017	0.0012
MZLULEP4538	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.538	6.523-6.549	6.433	6.415-6.453	6.285	6.266-6.306	NA
MZLULEP3661	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.406	6.387-6.418	6.356	6.343-6.373	6.202	6.185-6.224	NA
MZLULEP1710	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.633	6.617-6.649	6.620	6.605-6.634	6.580	6.557-6.602	0.0006
MZLULEP1824	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.450	6.429-6.465	6.452	6.435-6.468	6.439	6.418-6.462	NA
MZLULEP1709	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.237	6.228-6.253	6.115	6.101-6.135	6.031	6.014-6.048	0.0000
MZLULEP1911	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.677	6.657-6.691	6.649	6.632-6.668	6.572	6.55-6.589	NA
MZLULEP3656	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.293	6.28-6.302	6.177	6.162-6.192	6.069	6.049-6.086	0.0009
MZLULEP3668	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.093	6.076-6.104	5.984	5.969-6.002	5.830	5.814-5.849	NA
MZLULEP4316	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	6.441	6.427-6.457	6.430	6.417-6.448	6.347	6.327-6.366	NA
PI200	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.960	5.945-5.968	5.874	5.859-5.889	5.888	5.869-5.904	0.0004
PI201	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.958	5.943-5.963	5.799	5.784-5.815	5.795	5.774-5.813	0.0004
PI202	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.957	5.943-5.963	5.812	5.797-5.827	5.815	5.793-5.833	0.0004
PI203	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.920	5.905-5.927	5.751	5.738-5.766	5.732	5.709-5.749	0.0009
PI204	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.967	5.952-5.975	5.837	5.821-5.85	5.812	5.792-5.829	0.0006
PI205	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.930	5.916-5.937	5.833	5.818-5.848	5.820	5.801-5.837	0.0002
PI206	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.958	5.943-5.964	5.834	5.819-5.849	5.820	5.797-5.835	0.0000
PI207	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.956	5.942-5.962	5.773	5.758-5.788	5.772	5.751-5.79	0.0000
PI208	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.950	5.936-5.958	5.852	5.835-5.864	5.854	5.832-5.868	0.0000
PI413	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.955	5.94-5.961	6.280	6.265-6.294	6.323	6.303-6.34	0.0006
PI414	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.911	5.896-5.918	6.326	6.311-6.339	6.349	6.326-6.366	0.0000
PI415	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.956	5.942-5.963	6.378	6.363-6.393	6.424	6.4-6.44	0.0007
PI417	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.932	5.917-5.94	6.301	6.285-6.316	6.335	6.316-6.35	0.0007
PI418	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.950	5.936-5.958	6.344	6.326-6.358	6.370	6.347-6.387	0.0000
PI419	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.950	5.934-5.957	6.324	6.308-6.339	6.344	6.322-6.36	0.0000
PI420	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.925	5.91-5.932	6.292	6.277-6.31	6.316	6.294-6.331	0.0024
PI421	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.910	5.896-5.918	6.313	6.298-6.33	6.329	6.308-6.345	0.0011
PI422	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	Öland	5.928	5.913-5.934	6.319	6.303-6.335	6.367	6.345-6.384	0.0000
PI028	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.933	5.919-5.941	5.799	5.782-5.813	5.812	5.793-5.826	0.0011
PI029	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.877	5.861-5.883	5.811	5.795-5.826	5.810	5.788-5.826	0.0010
PI030	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.978	5.964-5.985	5.795	5.78-5.811	5.766	5.747-5.782	0.0000
PI031	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.915	5.9-5.922	5.780	5.765-5.794	5.758	5.736-5.775	0.0080
PI032	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.972	5.957-5.979	5.798	5.785-5.814	5.795	5.773-5.809	0.0000
PI033	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.861	5.847-5.868	5.747	5.732-5.763	5.740	5.718-5.758	0.0144
PI034	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.957	5.941-5.966	5.825	5.811-5.839	5.816	5.796-5.832	0.0000
PI035	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.950	5.935-5.957	5.883	5.866-5.897	5.873	5.849-5.89	0.0000
PI036	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	5.913	5.896-5.92	5.844	5.828-5.86	5.848	5.827-5.867	0.0006
MZLU153003	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	5.385	5.374-5.401	5.122	5.112-5.141	4.940	4.922-4.956	0.0015
MZLU153166	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.817	5.801-5.829	5.750	5.733-5.766	5.635	5.614-5.652	0.0028
MZLU153167	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.962	5.951-5.98	5.919	5.903-5.936	5.776	5.758-5.794	0.0041
MZLU153168	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.702	5.689-5.715	5.578	5.561-5.593	5.444	5.433-5.466	0.0055
MZLU153169	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Öland	6.029	6.015-6.04	6.161	6.143-6.173	6.049	6.033-6.069	0.0025
MZLU153170	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Öland	5.803	5.79-5.816	5.794	5.778-5.807	5.648	5.631-5.667	0.0076
MZLU153046	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Småland	6.848	6.831-6.862	7.293	7.276-7.312	7.244	7.223-7.264	0.0000
MZLU153040	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Småland	5.801	5.785-5.816	5.707	5.689-5.723	5.549	5.532-5.571	NA
MZLU153045	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Småland	4.968	4.952-4.979	4.907	4.896-4.922	4.717	4.699-4.734	NA
MZLU153042	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Småland	5.717	5.707-5.732	5.607	5.591-5.624	5.464	5.446-5.484	0.0061
MZLU153048	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	Småland	6.341	6.326-6.355	6.778	6.756-6.792	6.688	6.667-6.709	0.0293

MZLU152940	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	5.439	5.421-5.449	5.211	5.193-5.224	5.021	5.004-5.041	0.0159
PLAR0200	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	4.988	4.981-5.002	5.210	5.197-5.229	5.237	5.217-5.257	0.0053
PLAR0202	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.077	5.07-5.09	5.555	5.541-5.575	5.632	5.612-5.649	0.0000
PLAR0203	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.040	5.031-5.055	5.417	5.405-5.435	5.447	5.43-5.465	0.0016
PLAR0208	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.086	5.077-5.1	5.441	5.428-5.46	5.496	5.478-5.517	0.0017
PLAR0211	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.018	5.009-5.029	5.454	5.441-5.473	5.526	5.506-5.545	0.0132
PLAR0217	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.029	5.022-5.043	5.413	5.4-5.431	5.457	5.439-5.474	0.0014
PLAR0222	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.023	5.014-5.038	5.422	5.41-5.441	5.470	5.45-5.488	0.0063
PLAR0226	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	5.019	5.012-5.034	5.372	5.363-5.394	5.437	5.418-5.458	0.0018
MZLU107434	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.871	4.867-4.887	4.563	4.555-4.581	4.530	4.514-4.547	0.0085
MZLU107438	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.876	4.868-4.888	4.562	4.551-4.577	4.515	4.5-4.533	0.0124
MZLU107435	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.938	4.932-4.953	4.678	4.667-4.696	4.659	4.641-4.676	0.0074
MZLU107436	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.705	4.698-4.72	4.420	4.409-4.437	4.372	4.355-4.39	0.0406
MZLU107445	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.845	4.839-4.86	4.512	4.503-4.531	4.482	4.465-4.501	0.0288
MZLU107449	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.844	4.838-4.859	4.500	4.489-4.516	4.463	4.447-4.48	0.0118
MZLU107451	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.911	4.904-4.925	4.590	4.579-4.607	4.553	4.537-4.569	0.0011
MZLU107471	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.887	4.88-4.899	4.607	4.594-4.623	4.571	4.553-4.586	0.0121
MZLU107477	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.808	4.799-4.82	4.612	4.598-4.631	4.585	4.567-4.6	0.0025
MZLU107487	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.681	4.674-4.693	4.488	4.478-4.503	4.459	4.443-4.475	0.0291
MZLU107470	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Småland	4.921	4.914-4.936	4.612	4.601-4.628	4.572	4.551-4.587	0.0009
MZLU107486	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Småland	4.755	4.746-4.766	4.694	4.683-4.714	4.694	4.675-4.711	0.0192
MZLU107469	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Småland	4.893	4.886-4.906	4.649	4.638-4.665	4.636	4.619-4.652	0.0000
MZLU107483	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	Småland	4.698	4.687-4.709	4.641	4.628-4.656	4.617	4.597-4.635	0.0107
MZLU107426	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.890	4.883-4.905	4.621	4.613-4.639	4.574	4.557-4.59	0.0102
MZLU107439	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.867	4.854-4.879	4.557	4.544-4.574	4.526	4.51-4.541	0.0203
MZLU107441	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.818	4.814-4.833	4.581	4.571-4.599	4.542	4.525-4.557	0.0188
MZLU107443	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.964	4.957-4.977	4.621	4.611-4.638	4.576	4.56-4.592	0.0089
MZLU107468	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.847	4.839-4.86	4.569	4.559-4.585	4.525	4.507-4.543	0.0070
MZLU107475	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.980	4.974-4.998	4.597	4.586-4.616	4.569	4.551-4.586	0.0014
MZLU107480	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Modern	SW Skåne	4.797	4.792-4.813	4.688	4.679-4.709	4.668	4.652-4.687	0.0080
MZLU153246	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	4.565	4.553-4.576	4.748	4.731-4.761	4.699	4.683-4.719	0.0044
MZLU153247	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	4.490	4.475-4.499	4.720	4.704-4.73	4.684	4.669-4.702	0.0031
MZLU153248	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	4.740	4.726-4.748	5.014	4.997-5.028	4.982	4.964-4.999	0.0047
MZLU153251	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	4.370	4.359-4.38	4.564	4.551-4.577	4.512	4.499-4.534	0.0310
MZLU153250	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	E Skåne	4.912	4.897-4.92	5.883	5.866-5.897	5.881	5.86-5.898	0.0000
MZLU152770	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Småland	4.692	4.677-4.702	5.008	4.99-5.023	5.004	4.987-5.021	0.0138
MZLU152769	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Småland	4.168	4.156-4.175	4.549	4.534-4.56	4.514	4.499-4.529	0.0027
MZLU152765	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Småland	4.910	4.896-4.924	4.923	4.911-4.941	4.965	4.944-4.981	NA
MZLU152766	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	Småland	4.321	4.308-4.334	4.327	4.313-4.341	4.267	4.25-4.283	0.0008
MZLU153204	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	4.553	4.543-4.565	4.907	4.894-4.923	4.877	4.863-4.897	0.0259
MZLU153205	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	4.596	4.582-4.604	4.845	4.828-4.856	4.806	4.79-4.825	0.0032
MZLU153206	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	4.401	4.389-4.413	4.417	4.401-4.429	4.347	4.332-4.364	0.0090
MZLU153216	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	4.590	4.581-4.602	4.620	4.605-4.632	4.573	4.559-4.591	0.0000
MZLU153221	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	4.221	4.21-4.233	4.130	4.117-4.141	4.038	4.023-4.055	0.0019
MZLU107454	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.866	3.856-3.874	3.693	3.682-3.706	3.692	3.677-3.704	0.0079
MZLU107458	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.788	3.777-3.795	3.676	3.662-3.687	3.674	3.655-3.686	0.0224
MZLU107463	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.774	3.764-3.782	3.625	3.614-3.637	3.620	3.605-3.634	0.0325
MZLU107466	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.866	3.856-3.874	3.693	3.682-3.705	3.673	3.657-3.686	0.0064
MZLU107503	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.728	3.717-3.735	3.638	3.626-3.65	3.629	3.613-3.641	0.0237
MZLU107504	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.832	3.822-3.84	3.715	3.703-3.727	3.699	3.683-3.714	0.0159
MZLU107506	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.800	3.786-3.804	3.669	3.655-3.683	3.646	3.626-3.657	0.0147
MZLU107507	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	E Skåne	3.836	3.826-3.844	3.653	3.641-3.665	3.642	3.627-3.658	0.0087
CYSE0078	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	2.693	2.691-2.707	3.001	3.006-3.032	3.057	3.049-3.076	0.3263
CYSE0094	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.244	3.236-3.255	3.744	3.737-3.764	3.827	3.807-3.837	0.1854
CYSE0096	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.663	3.649-3.668	3.998	3.985-4.013	4.082	4.066-4.098	0.1172
CYSE0098	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.427	3.415-3.433	3.921	3.907-3.935	3.992	3.975-4.009	0.1403
CYSE0116	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.600	3.586-3.606	3.934	3.92-3.945	3.990	3.971-4.002	0.0896
CYSE0198	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.679	3.67-3.687	4.170	4.157-4.185	4.258	4.238-4.272	0.0734
CYSE0199	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	SE Skåne	3.493	3.483-3.5	3.937	3.922-3.949	4.033	4.02-4.052	0.1333
MZLU107461	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.701	3.691-3.709	3.837	3.822-3.849	3.876	3.855-3.888	0.0174
MZLU107462	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.774	3.765-3.782	3.579	3.567-3.591	3.555	3.536-3.569	0.0014
MZLU107465	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.154	3.132-3.149	2.918	2.903-2.926	2.901	2.877-2.904	0.1699
MZLU107455	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.709	3.698-3.716	3.644	3.631-3.658	3.628	3.612-3.641	0.0028
MZLU107456	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.168	3.16-3.178	3.136	3.125-3.147	3.140	3.125-3.154	0.1458
MZLU107501	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	Småland	3.458	3.449-3.465	3.421	3.41-3.435	3.418	3.403-3.433	0.0721
MZLU107457	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.658	3.646-3.665	3.490	3.476-3.502	3.476	3.461-3.49	0.0599
MZLU107460	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.650	3.64-3.657	3.538	3.528-3.55	3.505	3.49-3.516	0.0581
MZLU107464	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.770	3.759-3.777	3.583	3.572-3.595	3.588	3.572-3.602	0.0293
MZLU107497	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.555	3.546-3.563	3.454	3.442-3.464	3.444	3.43-3.456	0.0733
MZLU107498	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.715	3.704-3.722	3.578	3.563-3.588	3.568	3.552-3.582	0.0360
MZLU107499	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.439	3.43-3.447	3.298	3.29-3.312	3.277	3.261-3.291	0.1182
MZLU107500	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.597	3.583-3.602	3.568	3.558-3.581	3.559	3.539-3.569	0.0670
MZLU107505	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.713	3.703-3.722	3.687	3.676-3.701	3.665	3.649-3.679	0.0474
MZLU166853	<i>Agriades optilete</i>	Historical	Småland	2.020	2.007-2.035	2.101	2.084-2.117	2.217	2.197-2.236	0.0000
MZLU107492	<i>Agriades optilete</i>	Modern	Småland	1.706	1.697-1.717	1.720	1.704-1.733	1.833	1.816-1.85	0.0000
MZLU166851	<i>Aricia agestis</i>	Historical	W Skåne	5.142	5.132-5.157	5.184	5.17-5.2	5.128	5.112-5.148	0.0923
MZLU107489	<i>Aricia agestis</i>	Modern	W Skåne	4.645	4.633-4.657	4.930	4.915-4.942	4.991	4.979-5.016	0.0740
MZLU166854	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Historical	Öland	4.884	4.86-4.903	NA	NA	4.884	4.86-4.903	NA
MZLU107493	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Modern	Öland	4.742	4.725-4.749	4.646	4.627-4.66	4.590	4.568-4.606	0.0000
MZLU174144	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Historical	W Skåne	1.585	1.576-1.592	1.281	1.273-1.29	0.985	0.977-0.993	NA
MZLU174145	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Historical	W Skåne	1.703	1.695-1.71	1.192	1.184-1.199	0.911	0.903-0.919	0.0000

MZLU174143	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Modern	W Skåne	2.024	2.015-2.03	1.365	1.356-1.372	1.049	1.039-1.056	0.0000
EK001	<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	Historical	W Skåne	3.008	2.994-3.025	2.933	2.916-2.951	2.960	2.941-2.983	0.0164
EK006	<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	Modern	W Skåne	2.359	2.347-2.375	2.012	1.998-2.029	1.991	1.971-2.011	0.0437
MZLU166850	<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	Historical	W Skåne	3.984	3.961-4.005	4.002	3.981-4.02	4.047	4.019-4.069	NA
MZLU107491	<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	Modern	W Skåne	3.288	3.27-3.303	3.320	3.298-3.338	3.394	3.371-3.415	NA
MZLU174141	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Historical	Södermanland	1.025	1.007-1.041	NA	NA	1.085	1.066-1.103	NA
MZLU174142	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Historical	Södermanland	1.326	1.311-1.341	1.441	1.424-1.461	1.650	1.626-1.671	NA
MZLU174140	<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Modern	Södermanland	0.521	0.509-0.535	NA	NA	0.573	0.558-0.587	NA

Table S3. Statistical testing of differences in heterozygosity between modern and historical samples. For each statistic, differences are tested for with an unequal variance t-test per species, and the change in mean estimates, t-value, and p-value of the tests are listed, with $p < 0.05$ highlighted in bold. This was performed for the samples at full sequencing depth as well as at 3X to account for variation in sequencing depth between samples. All three species exhibited significant declines in individual heterozygosity.

Species	Sample Depth	Method	Mean Change (modern-historical)	CI (Lower)	CI (Upper)	t-value	p-value
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Full	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-0.3442	-0.4235	-0.2649	8.8910	1.19E-09
<i>Po. icarus</i>	3X	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-0.1957	-0.3330	-0.0585	2.8614	0.00607
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Full	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-0.9185	-1.2218	-0.6151	6.6287	2.98E-05
<i>Pl. argus</i>	3X	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-1.0034	-1.4488	-0.5581	4.8328	0.00027
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Full	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-0.9396	-1.0995	-0.7796	12.0107	8.16E-13
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	3X	Welch Two-Sample t-test	-1.1474	-1.4039	-0.8909	9.3719	1.67E-08

Table S4. Estimates of pairwise nucleotide diversity, Watterson's θ , and Tajima's D for populations of focal species. For each focal species population, nucleotide diversity was estimated in 10kb windows for 100 subsamplings of 4 individuals to create even sample sizes. For each subsample, we inferred the genome-wide mean of each estimator, describing here the median, minimum, and maximum estimates from the 100 subsamples for each population.

Species	Region	Time Period	Year	Sequencing	Median	Min Nucleotide	Max Nucleotide	Median	Min	Max	Median	Min Tajima's D	Max Tajima's D
				Depth	Nucleotide	Diversity	Diversity	Watterson's θ	Watterson's θ	Watterson's θ	Tajima's D		
<i>Po. icarus</i>	E Skåne	Historical	1934	Full	0.00653	0.00642	0.00663	0.00832	0.00821	0.00844	-1.18461	-1.21414	-1.15631
<i>Po. icarus</i>	E Skåne	Historical	1934	3X	0.00633	0.00624	0.00637	0.00818	0.00805	0.00824	-1.22690	-1.24346	-1.21572
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Öland	Historical	1940	Full	0.00655	0.00633	0.00672	0.00814	0.00795	0.00826	-1.05504	-1.12656	-0.99120
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Öland	Historical	1940	3X	0.00611	0.00602	0.00618	0.00776	0.00763	0.00787	-1.15504	-1.16954	-1.14148
<i>Po. icarus</i>	W Skåne	Historical	1934	Full	0.00662	0.00644	0.00675	0.00841	0.00823	0.00853	-1.16556	-1.22031	-1.10118
<i>Po. icarus</i>	W Skåne	Historical	1934	3X	0.00638	0.00626	0.00652	0.00823	0.00806	0.00843	-1.22380	-1.24401	-1.20431
<i>Po. icarus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2020	Full	0.00648	0.00646	0.00650	0.00784	0.00783	0.00787	-0.95170	-0.95664	-0.94458
<i>Po. icarus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2020	3X	0.00601	0.00599	0.00604	0.00743	0.00739	0.00747	-1.04818	-1.05452	-1.03961
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Öland	Modern	2020	Full	0.00651	0.00650	0.00653	0.00777	0.00775	0.00779	-0.88147	-0.88553	-0.87688
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Öland	Modern	2020	3X	0.00627	0.00626	0.00628	0.00777	0.00775	0.00779	-1.06078	-1.06655	-1.05398
<i>Po. icarus</i>	W Skåne	Modern	2020	Full	0.00646	0.00634	0.00649	0.00782	0.00752	0.00786	-0.95235	-0.95910	-0.84411
<i>Po. icarus</i>	W Skåne	Modern	2020	3X	0.00601	0.00593	0.00603	0.00743	0.00713	0.00745	-1.04815	-1.05168	-0.93050
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Småland	Historical	1936	Full	0.00600	0.00584	0.00614	0.00726	0.00705	0.00746	-0.95193	-0.96436	-0.93554
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Småland	Historical	1936	3X	0.00587	0.00565	0.00599	0.00734	0.00699	0.00753	-1.09640	-1.12105	-1.04725
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Öland	Historical	1951	Full	0.00603	0.00599	0.00606	0.00717	0.00711	0.00719	-0.85526	-0.87770	-0.84183
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Öland	Historical	1951	3X	0.00569	0.00563	0.00571	0.00702	0.00692	0.00705	-1.03674	-1.04232	-1.02096
<i>Pl. argus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2022	Full	0.00529	0.00527	0.00530	0.00597	0.00594	0.00600	-0.60370	-0.61868	-0.59143
<i>Pl. argus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2022	3X	0.00524	0.00521	0.00528	0.00606	0.00602	0.00614	-0.75333	-0.77488	-0.74281
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Småland	Modern	2021	Full	0.00513	0.00502	0.00520	0.00568	0.00535	0.00582	-0.48333	-0.55406	-0.28860
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Småland	Modern	2021	3X	0.00477	0.00467	0.00484	0.00530	0.00502	0.00544	-0.55110	-0.61884	-0.38756
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Öland	Modern	2021	Full	0.00520	0.00514	0.00525	0.00575	0.00566	0.00583	-0.49668	-0.51432	-0.46852
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Öland	Modern	2021	3X	0.00478	0.00475	0.00481	0.00531	0.00524	0.00536	-0.55781	-0.57951	-0.52709
<i>Pl. argus</i>	SW Skåne	Modern	2021	Full	0.00524	0.00519	0.00529	0.00583	0.00577	0.00590	-0.51594	-0.52660	-0.50717
<i>Pl. argus</i>	SW Skåne	Modern	2021	3X	0.00483	0.00482	0.00485	0.00540	0.00538	0.00542	-0.57943	-0.58901	-0.57384
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	Historical	1956	Full	0.00463	0.00458	0.00466	0.00555	0.00547	0.00559	-0.88482	-0.89649	-0.87332
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	Historical	1956	3X	0.00467	0.00451	0.00469	0.00588	0.00561	0.00590	-1.11573	-1.11936	-1.06408
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Småland	Historical	1936	Full	0.00445	0.00445	0.00445	0.00526	0.00526	0.00526	-0.83121	-0.83121	-0.83121
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Småland	Historical	1936	3X	0.00443	0.00443	0.00443	0.00542	0.00542	0.00542	-0.99700	-0.99700	-0.99700
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	Historical	1951	Full	0.00439	0.00436	0.00455	0.00506	0.00502	0.00546	-0.71678	-0.89434	-0.70338
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	Historical	1951	3X	0.00428	0.00422	0.00446	0.00510	0.00501	0.00555	-0.87049	-1.06453	-0.85076
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2021	Full	0.00399	0.00396	0.00404	0.00457	0.00451	0.00468	-0.66096	-0.71288	-0.60803
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	Modern	2021	3X	0.00376	0.00373	0.00378	0.00433	0.00422	0.00438	-0.70484	-0.74530	-0.63799
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Småland	Modern	2021	Full	0.00373	0.00359	0.00382	0.00394	0.00362	0.00418	-0.24844	-0.43564	-0.01286
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Småland	Modern	2021	3X	0.00352	0.00339	0.00359	0.00371	0.00347	0.00396	-0.28996	-0.50815	-0.05672
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	Modern	2022	Full	0.00357	0.00340	0.00368	0.00367	0.00343	0.00387	-0.11723	-0.22473	0.00060
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	Modern	2022	3X	0.00361	0.00344	0.00373	0.00381	0.00356	0.00402	-0.32662	-0.41410	-0.21144
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	Modern	2021	Full	0.00381	0.00374	0.00386	0.00416	0.00403	0.00425	-0.41195	-0.46279	-0.34597
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	Modern	2021	3X	0.00359	0.00354	0.00365	0.00391	0.00380	0.00402	-0.44228	-0.50006	-0.37015

Table S5. Statistical testing of differences between modern and historical populations for nucleotide diversity, Watterson's θ , and Tajima's D. Only comparisons between geographically proximal (<40km) sampling sites across time periods are shown. To account for variation in sample size, each population was subsampled to 4 individuals 100 times. For each of the 100 subsamples, 10kb sliding windowed estimates (5kb step) were compared between the modern and historical population with a Wilcoxon ranked sign test, pairing windows. The metrics below are derived from the median of each of the 100 subsamples: the change in each diversity/neutrality estimate (Δ), the Z-score from the statistical test, and the effect size of the test (estimated as $Z/\sqrt{N_{\text{windows}}}$). Comparisons where the effect sizes of all 100 subsamples did not overlap 0 were considered significant and have their effect sizes in bold. For the diversity statistics, the proportion diversity retained over the time period, the proportion retained per year, and the percent retained over a period of 100 years are shown. The latter is used to assign a threat category to the rate of genomic decline using the indicators outlined by Andersson et al. (4). To account for variation in sequencing depth, all estimates were additionally estimated with individuals subsampled to 3X sequencing depth. This subsampling largely does not change the results for *P. argus* and *C. semiargus*, but does affect the strength/direction of some diversity changes in *P. icarus*, where effects were already weaker.

Species	Modern Region	Modern Year	Historical Region	Historical Year	Sequencing Depth	Nucleotide diversity						
						Δ Nucleotide Diversity	Proportion retained	Proportion retained / year	% retained per 100 years	Threat category	Median Z-score	Median Effect Size
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	Full	-0.00024	0.9620	0.9995	95.60	Acceptable	-35.05	-0.120
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	3X	-0.00007	0.9894	0.9999	98.77	Acceptable	4.055	0.014
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	Full	-0.00021	0.9659	0.9996	95.76	Acceptable	-32.1	-0.110
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	3X	0.00016	1.0261	1.0003	103.28	Acceptable	51.1	0.176
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	Full	-0.00033	0.9485	0.9994	94.04	Warning	-54.15	-0.186
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	3X	-0.00014	0.9771	0.9997	97.34	Acceptable	-12.05	-0.042
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	Full	-0.00085	0.8539	0.9977	79.80	Warning	-160.5	-0.611
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	3X	-0.00056	0.9002	0.9985	86.05	Warning	-104	-0.397
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	-0.00087	0.8503	0.9981	82.64	Warning	-159	-0.606
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	-0.00079	0.8642	0.9983	84.22	Warning	-136	-0.519
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	Full	-0.00062	0.8591	0.9977	79.16	Warning	-172	-0.610
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	3X	-0.00071	0.8456	0.9974	77.26	Warning	-173.5	-0.617
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	Full	-0.00102	0.7680	0.9960	67.04	Alarm	-215	-0.762
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	3X	-0.00110	0.7569	0.9958	65.57	Alarm	-214.5	-0.763
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	-0.00072	0.8301	0.9978	80.33	Warning	-182	-0.646
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	-0.00074	0.8291	0.9978	80.21	Warning	-175	-0.623
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	Full	-0.00059	0.8598	0.9978	80.59	Warning	-159	-0.564
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	3X	-0.00055	0.8670	0.9980	81.55	Warning	-144	-0.513

Species	Modern Region	Modern Year	Historical Region	Historical Year	Sequencing Depth	Watterson's θ						
						Δ Watterson's θ	Proportion retained	Proportion retained / year	% retained per 100 years	Threat category	Median Z-score	Median Effect Size
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	Full	-0.00060	0.9258	0.9991	91.42	Warning	-92.85	-0.319
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	3X	-0.00048	0.9401	0.9993	93.07	Warning	-70.3	-0.242
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	Full	-0.00047	0.9394	0.9992	92.48	Warning	-75.05	-0.257
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	3X	-0.00016	0.9789	0.9997	97.37	Acceptable	-15.75	-0.054
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	Full	-0.00070	0.9144	0.9990	90.12	Warning	-110	-0.377
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	3X	-0.00057	0.9292	0.9991	91.82	Warning	-85	-0.293
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	Full	-0.00140	0.7969	0.9968	72.30	Alarm	-194	-0.738
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	3X	-0.00131	0.8099	0.9970	74.00	Alarm	-179	-0.683
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	-0.00155	0.7763	0.9970	74.23	Alarm	-201.5	-0.768
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	-0.00169	0.7665	0.9969	73.13	Alarm	-201	-0.768
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	Full	-0.00093	0.8232	0.9970	74.13	Alarm	-188	-0.667
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	3X	-0.00130	0.7752	0.9961	67.59	Alarm	-214	-0.761
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	Full	-0.00183	0.6548	0.9936	52.64	Alarm	-237	-0.841
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	3X	-0.00218	0.6158	0.9927	47.97	Alarm	-241	-0.857
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	-0.00130	0.7412	0.9965	70.30	Alarm	-221.5	-0.786
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	-0.00150	0.7147	0.9961	67.36	Alarm	-227.5	-0.810
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	Full	-0.00094	0.8045	0.9969	73.29	Alarm	-185.5	-0.658
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	3X	-0.00108	0.7822	0.9965	70.40	Alarm	-197	-0.701

Species	Modern Region	Modern Year	Historical Region	Historical Year	Sequencing Depth	Tajima's D		
						Δ Tajima's D	Median Z-score	Median Effect Size
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	Full	0.18866	175.5	0.602
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	E Skåne	1934	3X	0.22386	197	0.678
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	Full	0.13812	124	0.424
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	Öland	1940	3X	0.22340	183	0.630
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	Full	0.17125	164	0.563
<i>P. icarus</i>	W Skåne	2020	W Skåne	1934	3X	0.22070	194	0.670
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	Full	0.31997	177.5	0.676
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	Öland	1951	3X	0.48986	216	0.824
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	0.42365	205	0.781
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	0.55867	221	0.844
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	Full	0.19356	118.5	0.420
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	E Skåne	1956	3X	0.39752	209	0.744
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	Full	0.73973	226	0.802
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	E Skåne	1956	3X	0.95765	240	0.854
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	Full	0.54534	214.5	0.761
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	Småland	1936	3X	0.70415	235	0.836
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	Full	0.29980	145.5	0.516
<i>C. semiargus</i>	W Skåne	2021	W Skåne	1951	3X	0.47347	204.5	0.728

Table S6. Genetic differentiation between populations of the focal species. We estimated genetic differentiation using pairwise F_{ST} between populations within each time period. We estimated this both for the full sequencing depth data, as well as with all samples subsampled to 3X sequencing depth. Both unweighted and weighted F_{ST} are presented below, while the weighted estimate is used in the manuscript where discussed.

Species	Region 1	Region 1 Year	Region 2	Region 2 Year	Time Period	Distance (km)	Full Depth		3X Depth	
							Fst (unweighted)	Fst (weighted)	Fst (unweighted)	Fst (weighted)
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	1934	W Skåne	1934	Historical	50.01	0.00000	0.00000	0.00001	0.00000
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	1934	Öland	1940	Historical	170.71	0.00068	0.00426	0.00071	0.00077
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	1940	W Skåne	1934	Historical	212.33	0.00064	0.00483	0.00125	0.00716
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	W Skåne	2020	Modern	47.65	0.00013	0.00353	0.00342	0.01345
<i>P. icarus</i>	E Skåne	2020	Öland	2020	Modern	178.28	0.00028	0.00874	0.00372	0.01759
<i>P. icarus</i>	Öland	2020	W Skåne	2020	Modern	221.18	0.00035	0.01032	0.00380	0.02005
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	1936	Öland	1951	Historical	147.3	0.00060	0.00000	0.00116	0.00000
<i>P. argus</i>	E Skåne	2022	SW Skåne	2021	Modern	87.5	0.00063	0.01929	0.00776	0.02312
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	Öland	2021	Modern	173.36	0.00079	0.02949	0.00799	0.02102
<i>P. argus</i>	E Skåne	2022	Öland	2021	Modern	182.25	0.00075	0.02358	0.00747	0.02483
<i>P. argus</i>	E Skåne	2022	Småland	2021	Modern	193.41	0.00075	0.02530	0.00732	0.02134
<i>P. argus</i>	Småland	2021	SW Skåne	2021	Modern	244.67	0.00089	0.03416	0.00950	0.03428
<i>P. argus</i>	Öland	2021	SW Skåne	2021	Modern	268.99	0.00083	0.03266	0.00884	0.03598
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	1956	W Skåne	1951	Historical	45.61	0.00102	0.00622	0.00593	0.01112
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	1956	Småland	1936	Historical	166.1	0.00170	0.00695	0.00438	0.00952
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	1936	W Skåne	1951	Historical	193.88	0.00187	0.01183	0.00440	0.00983
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	SE Skåne	2022	Modern	43.61	0.00162	0.07959	0.01570	0.08013
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	W Skåne	2021	Modern	44.34	0.00092	0.04394	0.01393	0.04892
<i>C. semiargus</i>	SE Skåne	2022	W Skåne	2021	Modern	49.72	0.00209	0.10245	0.01558	0.10594
<i>C. semiargus</i>	E Skåne	2021	Småland	2021	Modern	191.11	0.00110	0.05495	0.01833	0.05870
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	W Skåne	2021	Modern	206.5	0.00156	0.07705	0.01530	0.08296
<i>C. semiargus</i>	Småland	2021	SE Skåne	2022	Modern	234.47	0.00226	0.11256	0.01694	0.11288

Table S7. Statistical assessment of differences in genetic differentiation between historical and modern samples. We assessed changes in genetic differentiation using estimates of pairwise F_{ST} between populations from the same time grouping (modern or historical). We performed two possible types of tests, one that included only population pairs where a similar geographic pairing existed in both time periods, for which we performed a paired t-test, pairing the corresponding localities. When the species had population pairs that could not be matched directly across time groups, we additionally performed an unequal variance t-test between all historical F_{ST} values and all modern F_{ST} values, including population pairs that are only present in one time grouping. We find that genetic differentiation increased significantly in *Po. icarus* and *Cy. semiargus*, even after subsampling to 3X sequencing depth to account for variance in sequencing coverage. As we only sequenced two historical populations for *Pl. argus*, we only had one historical data point for genetic differentiation, and could not statistically assess it, but present the mean differences in differentiation between the time periods.

Species	Sample Depth	Included Pairs	Method	Mean Difference				
				(Modern-Historical)	CI(lower)	CI(upper)	t-value	p-value
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Full	Pairs in both mod and hist	Paired t-test	0.0045	0.0021	0.0069	7.97	0.0154
<i>Po. icarus</i>	3X	Pairs in both mod and hist	Paired t-test	0.0144	0.0091	0.0197	11.74	0.0072
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Full	All population pairs	Insufficient population pairs (Modern = 6, Historical = 1)	0.0274	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Pl. argus</i>	3X	All population pairs	Insufficient population pairs (Modern = 6, Historical = 1)	0.0268	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Full	Pairs in both mod and hist	Insufficient population pairs in both time periods (N = 1)	0.0295	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Pl. argus</i>	3X	Pairs in both mod and hist	Insufficient population pairs in both time periods (N = 1)	0.0210	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Full	All population pairs	Welch Two Sample t-test	0.0701	0.0424	0.0978	6.42	0.0011
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	3X	All population pairs	Welch Two Sample t-test	0.0714	0.0450	0.0978	6.94	0.0009
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Full	Pairs in both mod and hist	Paired t-test	0.0503	0.0158	0.0848	6.27	0.0245
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	3X	Pairs in both mod and hist	Paired t-test	0.0534	0.0086	0.0982	5.13	0.0360

Table S8. Convergence results for admixture analyses. For values of K 1-10, we performed up to 100 replicate admixture analyses per species to assess convergence, performing a minimum of 20 replicates. If the three highest likelihood replicates were within 2 log-likelihood units of each other, the replicates were considered converged and no further replicates were performed. We selected the highest value of K per species that converged as the 'best fit', which are highlighted here in bold, presented with the total number of replicates required to reach convergence, as well as the difference in log-likelihood between the top 3 replicates.

Species	K	Replicates to convergence (max 100)	Δ log-likelihood of top 3 replicates
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	1	20	0.000
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	2	20	0.397
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	3	100	633.140
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	4	100	3648.154
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	5	100	3735.885
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	6	100	8932.071
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	7	100	9546.732
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	8	100	1900.623
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	9	100	14612.202
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	10	100	3196.896
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	1	20	0.000
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	2	82	0.002
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	3	100	7.598
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	4	100	613.156
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	5	100	64.614
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	6	100	9394.108
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	7	100	5139.375
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	8	100	11693.870
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	9	100	1150.451
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	10	100	9554.026
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	1	20	0.000
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	2	20	0.003
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	3	20	0.029
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	4	20	0.001
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	5	23	0.001
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	6	100	1723.171
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	7	100	2437.690
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	8	100	3294.573
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	9	100	10721.538
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	10	100	1766.152

Table S9. Statistical testing of differences in inbreeding between modern and historical samples. For each statistic, differences are tested for with an unequal variance t-test per species, and the change in mean estimates, t-value, and p-value of the tests are listed, with $p < 0.05$ highlighted in bold. Tests for differences in Froh are only performed at 5X sequencing depth, as these estimates are generated from samples subsampled to 5X for genotype calling. Only *Cy. semiargus* has experienced a significant increase in individual inbreeding coefficients.

Species	Method	Mean Change			t-value	p-value
		(modern-historical)	CI(Lower)	CI(Upper)		
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	0.0007	-0.0005	0.0020	1.18	0.24715
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	0.0037	-0.0026	0.0101	1.22	0.23414
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	0.0651	0.0371	0.0931	4.74	0.00005

Table S10. Statistical testing of differences in deleterious burden between modern and historical samples. We estimated deleterious burden for three categories of variants: conserved sites (those in the top 1% of GERP scores across the genome), high impact variants (e.g. loss of function, signifying strongly deleterious), and moderate impact variants (e.g. missense, signifying weakly deleterious). For each of these categories, we estimated total relative count of putatively deleterious alleles per individual. For conserved sites, this is the total derived allele count, scaled by the GERP score of each derived allele, per 1000 derived alleles. For high and moderate impact sites, this is the alternate allele count at these positions per 1000 alternate alleles. For homozygous deleterious burden, the same calculations are used, but only homozygous derived/alternate genotypes are counted in the numerator. We tested for differences using an unequal variance t-test per species, grouping historical and modern samples, with the outputs of these tests presented in this table. Total deleterious burden showed a significant decrease from historical to modern samples at strongly deleterious (high impact) sites for *Pl. argus* and *Cy. semiargus* as well as in weakly deleterious (moderate impact) sites in *Pl. argus*. Homozygous deleterious burden had a significant increase at conserved sites in *Pl. argus* and *Cy. semiargus* and at moderate impact sites in *Cy. semiargus*.

Species	Method	Variant Group	Total deleterious mutation burden							Homozygous deleterious mutation burden						
			Deleterious allele count per 1000 alt/der (modern)	Deleterious allele count per 1000 alt/der (historical)	Mean Difference (Modern-Historical)	CI (Lower)	CI (Upper)	t-value	p-value	Homozyg. Del. allele count per 1000 alt/der (modern)	Homozyg. Del. allele count per 1000 alt/der (historical)	Mean Difference (Modern-Historical)	CI (Lower)	CI (Upper)	t-value	p-value
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Conserved sites (GERP)	485.9774	488.3879	-2.4104	-16.9929	12.1721	-0.3402	0.73649	116.1619	107.8393	8.3226	-3.5122	20.1575	1.4513	0.15963
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	High Impact/LoF	0.5930	0.5928	0.0002	-0.0288	0.0292	0.0131	0.98960	0.2349	0.2264	0.0085	-0.0110	0.0281	0.8831	0.38273
<i>Po. icarus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Moderate Impact/Missense	30.8055	31.1187	-0.3132	-0.9187	0.2923	-1.0920	0.29019	13.9635	14.0118	-0.0484	-0.2978	0.2011	-0.3974	0.69415
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Conserved sites (GERP)	523.6616	522.6048	1.0568	-12.9793	15.0929	0.1558	0.87755	139.5266	118.1809	21.3457	12.5612	30.1303	5.0212	0.00004
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	High Impact/LoF	0.7346	0.8709	-0.1363	-0.2450	-0.0277	-2.7581	0.01843	0.3376	0.3225	0.0151	-0.0304	0.0606	0.7081	0.49004
<i>Pl. argus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Moderate Impact/Missense	42.4317	44.8945	-2.4628	-3.1758	-1.7498	-7.4990	6.0E-06	20.9434	21.2342	-0.2909	-0.7141	0.1324	-1.4315	0.16740
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Conserved sites (GERP)	526.4297	524.4805	1.9492	-13.0227	16.9212	0.2640	0.79325	137.5010	112.3936	25.1074	6.5756	43.6392	2.7467	0.00930
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	High Impact/LoF	0.6532	0.7247	-0.0715	-0.1358	-0.0072	-2.3260	0.03116	0.2868	0.2641	0.0227	-0.0260	0.0715	0.9551	0.34788
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	Welch Two Sample t-test	Moderate Impact/Missense	36.7471	37.8251	-1.0779	-2.2964	0.1406	-1.9122	0.07826	17.8472	16.1748	1.6724	0.7621	2.5827	3.7245	0.00066

Table S11. Predicted retention of heterozygosity over 100 years. We estimated the predicted percent of heterozygosity retained over 100 years, following Andersson et al (4) for each of the study species. We estimated this between all possible pairs of modern and historical samples for each study region for which a species had samples at multiple time points, using the time between the sampling of the individuals in the estimation. Here, the median of all possible pairs of individuals per grouping is shown, with the range of estimates given in parentheses for groups with more than a single individual per time period. We assigned a threat category to each of the median estimates, based on the thresholds described by Andersson et al. We performed this analysis for individual heterozygosity estimates at full sequencing depth, as well as with all individuals subsampled to 3X and 2X sequencing depth. Entries with NA are from species/populations for which individual sequencing depth was lower than the targeted subsampling depth.

Species	Study Region	2020 Swedish Red List	Full Sequencing Depth		3X Sequencing Depth		2X Sequencing Depth	
			Median heterozygosity retained over 100 years (range)	Threat Categorization	Median heterozygosity retained over 100 years (range)	Threat Categorization	Median heterozygosity retained over 100 years (range)	Threat Categorization
<i>Arcia agestis</i>	W Skåne	LC	88.35%	Warning	94.05%	Warning	96.75%	Acceptable
<i>Agriades optilete</i>	Småland	LC	75.49%	Warning	71.64%	Alarm	72.84%	Alarm
<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Öland	LC	95.86%	Acceptable	NA	NA	91.52%	Warning
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	E Skåne	LC	71.18% (40.23 - 82.82)	Alarm	67.94% (36.07 - 87.19)	Alarm	68.5% (37.11 - 91.6)	Alarm
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Småland	LC	72.9% (59.41 - 88.98)	Alarm	68.75% (52.97 - 86.81)	Alarm	68.83% (52.66 - 89.3)	Alarm
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	W Skåne	LC	73.91% (66.07 - 85.1)	Alarm	68% (56.67 - 85.04)	Alarm	68.14% (56.66 - 87.09)	Alarm
<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	W Skåne	EN	134.33% (127.53 - 141.12)	Acceptable	115.21% (109.32 - 121.1)	Acceptable	115.57% (109.14 - 122)	Acceptable
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	W Skåne	LC	80.60%	Warning	81.07%	Warning	82.05%	Warning
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	E Skåne	LC	93.64% (92.96 - 94.69)	Warning	105.54% (101.64 - 108.04)	Acceptable	110.08% (105.72 - 113.3)	Acceptable
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Öland	LC	75.98% (69.66 - 80.78)	Warning	70.11% (63.61 - 76.21)	Alarm	71.78% (64.67 - 78.24)	Alarm
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Småland	LC	79.45% (64.19 - 99.3)	Warning	77.34% (55.48 - 94.91)	Warning	79.19% (55.21 - 99.43)	Warning
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	W Skåne	LC	86.72% (85.15 - 89.32)	Warning	85.14% (84.2 - 87.31)	Warning	88.6% (87.52 - 91.07)	Warning
<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	W Skåne	CR	50.94%	Alarm	35.08%	Alarm	33.24%	Alarm
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	E Skåne	LC	93.29% (85.69 - 97.64)	Warning	93.07% (83.09 - 96.37)	Warning	94.42% (83.89 - 99.97)	Warning
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Öland	LC	96.04% (92.19 - 100.18)	Acceptable	107.84% (100.49 - 111.95)	Acceptable	112.13% (101.16 - 116.43)	Acceptable
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	W Skåne	LC	91.69% (85.93 - 97.82)	Warning	90.13% (84.41 - 98.05)	Warning	92.68% (85.33 - 100.86)	Warning
<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	Södermanland	EN	33.47% (27.34 - 39.59)	Alarm	NA	NA	32.38% (23.03 - 41.72)	Alarm

Table S12. Study species conservation status and reference genome information. For each study species, the conservation status in Sweden is presented based on the most recent assessment, the 2020 Swedish Red List. Sequencing data for each species was mapped to the closest available chromosome level reference genome. For the three focal species, as well as for two of the additional species, this was a species specific genome. For the other species, the reference genome species is listed in bold with a *. For inbreeding analyses, we utilized a recombination rate based off the assumption of 50 centimorgans per chromosome, which were used to calculate the autosomal recombination rates for the reference genome species in Morgans per base pair per generation.

Study Species	Swedish Red List 2020 Status	Reference species	RefSeq Assembly Accession	Assembly Name	Autosomal Chromosomes	Autosomal Length (bp)	Recombination rate (M/bp)
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	GCA_937595015.1	ilPollcar1.1	22	472204672	2.3295E-08
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	GCA_905404155.3	ilPleArgu1.3	22	360412310	3.05206E-08
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	GCA_905187585.1	ilCyaSemi1.1	23	416757882	2.7594E-08
<i>Agriades optilete</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>*	GCA_905187585.1	ilCyaSemi1.1	23	416757882	2.7594E-08
<i>Aricia agestis</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Aricia agestis</i>	GCF_905147365.1	ilAriAges1.1	22	394696725	2.78695E-08
<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	GCA_905187575.2	ilCelArgi3.2	24	468366633	2.5621E-08
<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	EN (Starkt hotad; Endangered)	<i>Phengaris arion</i>*	GCA_963565745.1	ilPheArio1.1	22	517794195	2.1244E-08
<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	CR (Akut hotad; Critically endangered)	<i>Plebejus argus</i>*	GCA_905404155.3	ilPleArgu1.3	22	360412310	3.05206E-08
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	LC (Livskraftig; Least Concern)	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>*	GCA_937595015.1	ilPollcar1.1	22	472204672	2.3295E-08
<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	EN (Starkt hotad; Endangered)	<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i>*	GCA_905404095.1	ilGlaAlex1.1	22	571088166	1.92615E-08

Table S13. Species dataset sequence data filtering. For each species dataset, we generated a 'filtered sites' file to limit analyses to. This filtered sites file is the intersection of several independent filters that remove scaffold smaller than 1Mb, non-autosomal contigs, repetitive regions, and regions in the top and bottom 1% of global sequencing depth for all sample, museum sample, and fresh sample groupings. Here, the number of base pairs and the proportion of the genome passing each filter is shown for each of the species datasets, as well as these parameters for the final combined filtered sites file. In some cases, only museum samples were utilized for a species, in which case the depth filters are only performed on one sample grouping, which is the same as the filtering across all samples. The reference genome used for each species is listed at the top of the table, and has a * when it is from a different species to the study species.

Filter	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i> (ilPollcar1.1)		<i>Plebejus argus</i> (ilPleArgu1.3)		<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i> (ilCyaSemi1.1)		<i>Aricia agestis</i> (ilAriAges2.1)		<i>Agriades optilete</i> (ilCyaSemi1.1*)	
	Filtered Length(bp)	Filtered percent	Filtered Length(bp)	Filtered percent	Filtered Length(bp)	Filtered percent	Length(bp)	Percent	Length(bp)	Percent
Total genome	511758028	100	382108302	100	441519306	100	437383100	100	441519306	100
Scaffolds<1000000bp	511184185	99.8879	379254911	99.2533	441467852	99.9883	437193358	99.9566	441467852	99.9883
Autosomes	472204672	92.2711	363250311	95.0648	416794061	94.4	394871022	90.2804	416794061	94.4
Repeats	214722289	41.9578	196284865	51.3689	205346149	46.509	203291869	46.4791	205346149	46.509
Depth (all)	432260793	84.4659	331051496	86.6381	391257204	88.6161	338871709	77.4771	183931694	41.6588
Depth (museum)	368471691	72.0012	277546440	72.6355	390545917	88.455	279823402	63.9767	167800752	38.0053
Depth (fresh)	429746613	83.9746	329708631	86.2867	355705831	80.564	330525236	75.5688	107150948	24.2687
Combined	181455194	35.4572	171521978	44.8883	179960301	40.7593	161788073	36.99	74627644	16.9025

Filter	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i> (ilCelArgi3.2)		<i>Phengaris alcon</i> (ilPheArio1.1*)		<i>Polyommatus amandus</i> (ilPollcar1.1*)		<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i> (ilPleArgu1.3*)		<i>Scolitantides orion</i> (ilGlaAlex1.1*)	
	Length(bp)	Percent	Length(bp)	Percent	Length(bp)	Percent	Length(bp)	Percent	Length(bp)	Percent
Total genome	499129456	100	544505416	100	511758028	100	382108302	100	619543730	100
Scaffolds<1000000bp	499081963	99.9905	544151925	99.9351	511184185	99.8879	379254911	99.2533	618774694	99.8759
Autosomes	468398789	93.8431	518131986	95.1564	472204672	92.2711	363250311	95.0648	571841974	92.3005
Repeats	216150827	43.3056	221163361	40.6173	214722289	41.9578	196284865	51.3689	214449644	34.6141
Depth (all)	359395148	72.0044	257300385	47.254	206146207	40.282	111063652	29.066	79497224	12.8316
Depth (museum)	353864347	70.8963	NA	NA	182782060	35.7165	NA	NA	NA	NA
Depth (fresh)	197675472	39.604	257300385	47.254	123896843	24.21	111063652	29.066	79497224	12.8316
Combined	118489307	23.7392	149563646	27.4678	82271209	16.0762	84407627	22.09	57776655	9.32568

Table S14. Removal of close-relatives from admixture/PCA. As close relatives can skew the results of principal component and admixture analyses, we removed third-degree and closer relatives from these analyses. We estimated relatedness using the IBSrelate method, identifying first degree (PO/FS; KING 0.25), second-degree (HS; KING 0.125), and third-degree (C1; KING 0.0625) relatives and removing one of each pair from the analyses. The removed individuals are highlight in bold and red text. These individuals were included in all other analyses.

Species	Sample 1	Sample 2	R0	R1	KING	Inferred Relationship
<i>Po. icarus</i>	PI031	PI033	0.3382	0.2854	0.0627	C1
<i>Pl. argus</i>	MZLU107435	MZLU107438	0.3155	0.2919	0.0722	C1
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	MZLU107455	MZLU107461	0.0332	0.7685	0.2857	FS
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	MZLU153216	MZLU153221	0.0789	0.5887	0.2327	FS
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	CYSE0078	CYSE0098	0.2254	0.3245	0.1131	HS
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	MZLU107456	MZLU107501	0.2471	0.3455	0.1088	HS
<i>Cy. semiargus</i>	CYSE0198	CYSE0199	0.2899	0.2905	0.0815	C1

Table S15. Reference genomes utilized for estimating GERP scores. We utilized the method implemented in the GenErode pipeline (13) to estimate GERP scores and ancestral states across the reference genomes for each species dataset. Below is the list of reference genomes, their accessions, and the reference species. We utilized all genomes from this list when estimating GERP scores and ancestral states along each of the focal species reference genomes, excluding the focal species.

RefSeq	Assembly	Accession	Assembly Name	Organism Name
GCA_902806685.2	iAphHyp	1.2	Maniola_hyperantus	Maniola_hyperantus
GCA_905147175.2	iAglUrti	1.2	Nymphalis_urticae	Nymphalis_urticae
GCA_905147235.1	iEryTage	1.1	Erynnis_tages	Erynnis_tages
GCA_905147285.1	iHypProb	1.1	Hypena_proboscidalis	Hypena_proboscidalis
GCA_905147375.1	iHylFasc	1.1	Hylaea_fasciaria	Hylaea_fasciaria
GCA_905147385.1	iLimCami	1.1	Limenitis_camilla	Limenitis_camilla
GCA_905147785.2	iThyBati	1.2	Thyatira_batis	Thyatira_batis
GCA_905163515.2	iLymMona	1.2	Lymantria_monacha	Lymantria_monacha
GCA_905187585.1	iCyaSemi	1.1	Cyaniris_semiargus	Cyaniris_semiargus
GCA_905220365.2	iVanCard	2.2	Vanessa_cardui	Vanessa_cardui
GCA_905220475.3	iEnnFusc	2.3	Ennomos_fuscantarius	Ennomos_fuscantarius
GCA_905220505.1	iLaoPopu	1.1	Laothoe_populi	Laothoe_populi
GCA_905220515.1	iLysCori	1.1	Lysandra_coridon	Lysandra_coridon
GCA_905220545.2	iMelAtha	1.2	Meliccta_athalia	Meliccta_athalia
GCA_905220585.2	iNymPoly	1.2	Nymphalis_polychloros	Nymphalis_polychloros
GCA_905231865.2	iBolSele	5.2	Boloria_selene	Boloria_selene
GCA_905332985.1	iMimTili	1.1	Mimas_tiliae	Mimas_tiliae
GCA_905333005.2	iLycPhla	1.2	Lycaena_phlaeas	Lycaena_phlaeas
GCA_905333045.1	iLysBell	1.1	Lysandra_bellargus	Lysandra_bellargus
GCA_905404095.1	iGlaAlex	1.1	Glaucopsyche_alexis	Glaucopsyche_alexis
GCA_905404115.1	iPheGnom	1.1	Pheosia_gnoma	Pheosia_gnoma
GCA_905404145.2	iBisBetu	1.2	Biston_betularia	Biston_betularia
GCA_905404155.3	iPleArgu	1.3	Plebejus_argus	Plebejus_argus
GCA_905404175.1	iAntCard	3.1	Anthocharis_cardamines	Anthocharis_cardamines
GCA_905404265.1	iFabAdip	1.1	Fabriciana_adippe	Fabriciana_adippe
GCA_905404285.2	iEraDefo	1.2	Erannis_defoliaria	Erannis_defoliaria
GCA_907269075.1	iIldaAver	1.1	Idaea_aversata	Idaea_aversata
GCA_910589475.2	iBemlchn	1.2	Bembecia_ichneumoniformis	Bembecia_ichneumoniformis
GCA_911387765.1	iPyrMalv	3.1	Pyrgus_malvae	Pyrgus_malvae
GCA_911387775.1	iThySylv	1.1	Thymelicus_sylvestris	Thymelicus_sylvestris
GCA_912999735.1	iApoCrat	1.1	Aporia_crataegi	Aporia_crataegi
GCA_914767645.1	iHydMica	1.1	Hydraecia_micacea	Hydraecia_micacea
GCA_914767915.1	iAgrAura	1.1	Agriopis_aurantiaria	Agriopis_aurantiaria
GCA_916614155.1	iMesFuru	1.1	Mesoligia_furuncula	Mesoligia_furuncula
GCA_916618145.1	iEmmMono	1.1	Emmelina_monodactyla	Emmelina_monodactyla
GCA_916999025.1	iOrgAnti	1.1	Orgyia_antiqua	Orgyia_antiqua
GCA_917051295.2	iEreLige	1.2	Erebia_ligea	Erebia_ligea

GCA_917862395.2	iHelSar1.2	Heliconius_sara
GCA_918358695.1	iMelMeno1.1	Melinaea_menophilus
GCA_918358865.1	iMelMars1.1	Melinaea_marsaeus
GCA_920104075.1	iMelGala2.1	Melanargia_galathea
GCA_921972225.1	iEupLuci1.1	Euplexia_lucipara
GCA_923060345.2	iEreAeth2.2	Erebia_aethiops
GCA_928268935.1	iLasMege1.1	Lasiommata_megera
GCA_932305915.1	iAgrMarg1.1	Agriopis_marginaria
GCA_932527185.1	iEclSila1.1	Ecliptopera_silaceata
GCA_933228805.2	iHipSeme1.2	Hipparchia_semele
GCA_937595015.1	iPollcar1.1	Polyommatus_icarus
GCA_937612035.1	iAriArta2.1	Aricia_artaxerxes
GCA_943138885.2	iThoDeci1.2	Tholera_decimalis
GCA_944567765.1	iCarPala2.1	Carterocephalus_palaemon
GCA_946902875.1	iNemSwae1.1	Nematopogon_swammerdamellus
GCA_947563715.1	iLycHirt1.1	Lycia_hirtaria
GCA_947579745.1	iApoHisp1.1	Apocheima_hispidaria
GCA_948253155.1	iLeuSali1.1	Leucoma_salicis
GCA_948474745.1	iOliLatr1.1	Oligia_latruncula
GCA_949126905.1	iAmoJugl1.1	Amorpha_juglandis
GCA_949316025.1	iLapConi1.1	Lapara_coniferarum
GCA_949316085.1	iHypScri1.1	Hypercompe_scribonia
GCA_949316135.1	iChoNemo1.1	Choreutis_nemorana
GCA_949316475.1	iHypPunc1.1	Hypomecis_punctinalis
GCA_949752805.1	iDeiElpe2.1	Deilephila_elpenor
GCA_949752895.1	iDenPini1.1	Dendrolimus_pini
GCA_950106695.1	iBisStrt2.1	Biston_stratarius
GCA_951213275.1	iIldaStra1.1	Idaea_straminata
GCA_951394245.1	iCycPunc2.1	Cyclophora_punctaria
GCA_951799465.1	iLepArip1.1	Leptophobia_aripa
GCA_951802675.2	iBolEuph2.2	Boloria_euphrosyne
GCA_951805285.1	iThyActe1.1	Thymelicus_acteon
GCA_958496195.1	iTimComa1.1	Timandra_comae
GCA_959347355.1	iNaplnac1.1	Napeogenes_inachia
GCA_959347395.1	iMecMaza1.1	Mechanitis_mazaeus
GCA_959347405.1	iNapSylp1.1	Napeogenes_sylphis
GCA_959347415.1	iMecMess1.1	Mechanitis_messenoides
GCA_963082625.1	iPasRect1.1	Pasiphila_rectangulata
GCA_963082685.1	iCycAlbi1.1	Cyclophora_albipunctata
GCA_963151315.1	iPolCalb1.1	Nymphalis_c-album
GCA_963422495.1	iPollphe1.1	Polyommatus_iphigenia
GCA_963555665.1	iDirLore1.1	Dircenna_loreta
GCA_963565295.1	iEpiAlte1.1	Epirrhoe_alternata
GCA_963565745.1	iPheArio1.1	Phengaris_arion
GCA_963576735.1	iBedSomn2.1	Bedellia_somnulentella

GCA_963669345.1	ilGorFlav1.1	Gortyna_flavago
GCA_963924445.1	ilPhiTran2.1	Philereme_transversata
GCA_963932025.1	ilEreEPIP2.1	Erebia_epiphron
GCA_963932265.1	ilThyLine1.1	Thymelicus_lineola
GCA_963969515.1	ilYpoEvon2.1	Yponomeuta_evonymella
GCA_964007245.1	ilHypAtoa1.1	Hypomecis_atomaria
GCA_964144555.1	ilHelCong3.1	Heliconius_congener
GCA_964145975.1	ilHelAnti3.1	Heliconius_antiochus
GCA_964147245.1	ilHelSaph4.1	Heliconius_sapho
GCA_964188065.1	ilEreAlbe1.1	Erebia_albergana
GCA_964258725.1	ilColHyal1.hap1.1	Colias_hyale
GCA_964260675.1	ilEreMont1.hap1.1	Erebia_montana
GCA_964261405.1	ilMelVari1.hap1.1	Mellicta_varia
GCF_905147045.1	ilAgllox1.1	Nymphalis_io
GCF_905147105.1	ilPieBrab1.1	Pieris_brassicae
GCF_905147365.1	ilAriAges1.1	Aricia_agestis
GCF_905147765.1	ilVanAtal1.2	Vanessa_atalanta
GCF_905147795.1	ilPieRapa1.1	Pieris_rapae
GCF_905163445.1	ilParAegt1.1	Pararge_aegeria
GCF_905220415.1	ilColCroc2.1	Colias_croceus
GCF_905220565.1	ilMelCinx1.1	Melitaea_cinxia
GCF_905333055.1	ilManJurt1.1	Maniola_jurtina
GCF_905404315.1	ilLepSina1.1	Leptidea_sinapis
GCF_905475465.1	ilPieNapi1.2	Pieris_napi
GCF_947172395.1	ilBicAnyn1.1	Bicyclus_anymana

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